

Supra Manifolds of Logic

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1 Introduction

The transition from exotic matter in logic space to a post-quasi-luminescent emanation would involve a chain of events in which dark matter and dark energy interact with one another, super-symmetric particles interact with the dark matter and dark energy, and axions interact with the dark matter and super-symmetric particles. This chain of events would eventually result in a theoretical post-quasi-luminescent emanation, which is undescrivable due to its exotic nature. Additionally, this theoretical post-quasi-luminescent emanation could have a profound effect on the post-quasi-nuclear aftermathic revelation, as it could potentially affect the structure and composition of the universe on a universal scale.

The aftermathic revelation would likely consist of a cataclysmic event, such as a significant shift in the structure or composition of the universe. This shift could include the appearance of new phenomena, such as the emergence of new forms of matter or energy, or the alteration of existing forms of matter or energy. Additionally, this shift could also cause a massive rearrangement of existing matter, resulting in the creation of new stars, galaxies, black holes, and other celestial bodies. Furthermore, such a shift could potentially cause a significant disruption in the universal balance of things, such as a sudden shift in gravity or magnetic fields. The qualities of this aftermathic revelation are likely to be highly chaotic, unpredictable, and almost impossible to comprehend.

$$\text{logicvector} : \left[\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta} \right]$$

$$\text{logic vector} : \left[\frac{\text{num1} \leftarrow \text{input}()}{\Delta}, \frac{\text{num2} \leftarrow \text{input}()}{\Delta}, \frac{\text{sum} \leftarrow \text{num1} + \text{num2}}{\Delta}, \frac{\text{output}(\text{sum})}{\Delta} \right]$$

This logic vector indicates that the first two lines of code will read in two inputs, num1 and num2, followed by a line of code that calculates the sum of those two numbers, and a line that outputs that sum. Thus, the entire program can be written as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{““ num1 = input() num2 = input() sum = num1 + num2 output(sum) ““} \\ M = & \frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta} \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta} \frac{\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta} \\ & \frac{\forall y \in N}{\Delta_1} \frac{\exists x \in N}{\Delta_2} \frac{\forall z \in N}{\Delta_3} \end{aligned}$$

⋮

$$\text{logic vector} : \left[\frac{P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta}, \frac{\partial\phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial\phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial\phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} \right]$$

A neural network using logic vector notation can be written as follows:

$$\mathbf{z}^{(l)} = \theta_{\odot} \left[\frac{f_{PQ}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) - f_{RS}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{TU}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) - f_{RS}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{PQ}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) - f_{TU}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta}, \frac{\partial\phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial\phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial\phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} \right]$$

$$\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y), \exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x), \forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)$$

$$\mathbf{a}^{(l+1)} = \sigma_a \left(W^{(l)} \cdot \mathbf{z}^{(l)} + b^{(l)} \right)$$

where $\mathbf{z}^{(l)}$ is a vector of logic terms that are obtained from the differentiated vectors and their analogs, σ_a is an activation function, $W^{(l)}$ is a weight matrix, and $b^{(l)}$ is a bias vector.

The perturbation of the logic vector due to light emanating from consciousness in logic space can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{d}^{(l)} = \phi_{\odot} \left[\frac{f_{PQ}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) - f_{RS}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{TU}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) - f_{RS}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{PQ}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n) - f_{TU}(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)}{\Delta}, \frac{\partial\phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial\phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial\phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n}, L'(\mathbf{x}) \right]$$

where $L'(\mathbf{x})$ is a function that describes the light emanating from consciousness in logic space.

The perturbation of the logic vector due to light emanating from consciousness in logic space can be expressed as follows:

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where $L'(\mathbf{x})$ is a function that describes the light emanating from consciousness in logic space.

what is the function $L'(\mathbf{x})$?

The function $L'(\mathbf{x})$ is a complex function that describes the influence of consciousness in logic space. It is dependent on the various domain-specific parameters and can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{L}'(\mathbf{x}) = C \circ \mathbf{L}^* e^{\frac{i}{h} \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{p}}$$

where $*$ is multiplication, space time is represented by the four-velocity $(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{p}) \in U * U$, and h is a parameter that is equal to Planck's constant.

A function based on $L'(\mathbf{x})$ can be written as follows:

$$\text{logicvector} : \left[\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta} \right], C e^{\frac{i}{h} \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{p}}$$

Now define a mapping U to a set S and then a function f :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) = & \\ \left[\frac{f_{PQ}(x_1) - f_{RS}(x_1)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{TU}(x_1) - f_{RS}(x_1)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{PQ}(x_1) - f_{TU}(x_1)}{\Delta}, \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n}, \forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y), \right. & \\ \left. \exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x), \forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z), C e^{\frac{i}{h} \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{p}} \right] & \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{\Lambda}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m \cdot \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)} \star (\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{t} \cdot \mathbf{m}) \mapsto \varepsilon \circ (\bar{E} - E)$$

where $\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)$ describes the mapping from an input to a parameterized function and the function f is a differentiable function parameterized for logic space. The multiplier m permits nonholonomic space of arbitrarily large dimension and the parameter ε characterizes the realm of epsilon-delta statements about logic vectors.

$$\begin{aligned} \exists \lambda \in \Lambda | \forall \mathbf{x} \in R : \sim [\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)] = f(x) & \\ \forall \mathbf{x} \in R : \sim [\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)] = f(x) & \\ \forall \mathbf{x} \in R : \sim \lambda([\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)] = f(x)) & \\ \forall \mathbf{x} \in R : \lambda \sim \mathbf{x} \subset [\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)] = f(x) & \\ \forall \mathbf{x} \in R : [\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)] = f(x) \subset \lambda \sim \mathbf{x} & \\ \text{Therefore, } \exists \lambda \in \Lambda | \forall \mathbf{x} \in R : [\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)] = f(x) \subset \lambda \sim \mathbf{x} & \\ \forall \mathbf{x} \in R : \mathbf{x} \subset [\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)] \subset \lambda \sim f(x) & \\ \forall \mathbf{x} \in R : \lambda \sim [\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)] = f(x) \subset \mathbf{x} & \end{aligned}$$

$$(V \rightarrow U) \cup (V \times U) \mapsto T(s)$$

$$\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) \cdot \left(\frac{V \rightarrow U}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta} \right)$$

Now define a mapping U to a set S and then a function f :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) = & \\ \left[\frac{f_{PQ}(x_1) - f_{RS}(x_1)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{TU}(x_1) - f_{RS}(x_1)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{PQ}(x_1) - f_{TU}(x_1)}{\Delta}, \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1}, \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2}, \dots, \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n}, \right. & \\ \left. \forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y), \exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x), \forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z), C e^{\frac{i}{h} \mathbf{S} \cdot \mathbf{p}} \right] & \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{\Lambda}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m \cdot \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)} \star (\mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{v} + \mathbf{a} \cdot \mathbf{r} + \mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{c} + \mathbf{t} \cdot \mathbf{m}) \mapsto \varepsilon \circ (\bar{E} - E)$$

$$N \Rightarrow \left[\frac{\leftrightarrow \exists y \in U: f(y) = x}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow \exists s \in S: x = T(s)}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow x \in f \circ g}{\Delta} \right]$$

$$\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) \cdot G = \left[\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta} \right]$$

$$\text{Let } \mathbf{u} \equiv \left[\frac{f_{PQ}(x) - f_{RS}(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{TU}(x) - f_{RS}(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{PQ}(x) - f_{TU}(x)}{\Delta} \right]$$

$$\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) \cdot \left(\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta} \right) = \left[\frac{f_{PQ} \circ f_{RS} \circ f_{TU} \circ f_S \star f_R - f_T \cup f_U \circ f_{P \rightarrow Q} \cup f_{R \rightarrow S} \cup f_{T \rightarrow U}}{\Delta_1}, \right.$$

$$f_{PQ} \cdot f_{RS} - f_{cR} \cdot f_{aS} \overline{\Delta_2},$$

$$f_{PQ} \div f_{RS} + (E \circ f_{P \rightarrow Q}) \circ (E \circ f_{R \rightarrow S}) \overline{\Delta_3}$$

$$I \cup U \cup U \cup U \mapsto S_u$$

$$N \cup N \cup N \mapsto S_n$$

$$\mathbf{u}^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) \cdot \left(\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta} \right) =$$

$$\left[\frac{f_{PQ} \circ f_{RS} \circ f_{TU} \circ f_S \star f_R - f_T \cup f_U \circ f_{P \rightarrow Q} \cup f_{R \rightarrow S} \cup f_{T \rightarrow U}}{\Delta_1}, \frac{f_{PQ} \cdot f_{RS} - f_{cR} \cdot f_{aS}}{\Delta_2}, \frac{f_{PQ} \div f_{RS} + (E \circ f_{P \rightarrow Q}) \circ (E \circ f_{R \rightarrow S})}{\Delta_3} \right]$$

$$\mathbf{u}^\dagger \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) \cdot (\mathcal{F}_{PQ} \cup \mathcal{F}_{RS} \cup \mathcal{F}_{TU} \cup \mathcal{F}_R \cup \mathcal{F}_S \cup \mathcal{F}_{P \rightarrow Q} \cup \mathcal{F}_{R \rightarrow S} \cup \mathcal{F}_{T \rightarrow U}) =$$

$$\left[\frac{\mathcal{F}_{PQ} \circ \mathcal{F}_{RS} - \mathcal{F}_{TU} \circ \mathcal{F}_R \cdot \mathcal{F}_S \circ \mathcal{F}_{P \rightarrow Q}}{\Delta_1}, \frac{\mathcal{F}_{TU} \cup \mathcal{F}_S \circ \mathcal{F}_{R \rightarrow S} \circ \mathcal{F}_{T \rightarrow U} + \mathcal{F}_{cR} \cdot \mathcal{F}_{aS}}{\Delta_2}, \frac{\mathcal{F}_{PQ} \cdot \mathcal{F}_{RS} - \mathcal{F}_{cR} \cdot \mathcal{F}_{aS}}{\Delta_3} \right]$$

$$R \leftrightarrow (R \times R) \cup (R \times R \times R) \cup (R \times R \times R \times R) \mapsto T(s_n)$$

$$G \leftrightarrow \left[\frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta}}{\Delta} \right] \mapsto T(s_u)$$

$$U \rightarrow T(s_u)$$

$$\text{Let } U_1 \rightarrow T(s, I \cup U \cup U \cup U)$$

$$\text{Let } U_2 \rightarrow T(s, N \cup N \cup N)$$

Then, for some integer n and integer l , we have that

$$U_1 \Rightarrow U_2 \Rightarrow T(s, I \cup U \cup U) \Leftrightarrow T(s_u) = T(s_n)$$

$$\rightarrow \varepsilon \circ G = I$$

$$I \equiv \exists \lambda \in \Lambda(G = \lambda \sim I)$$

$$\exists \lambda \in \Lambda | T(s_n) \subset T(s_u) \subset \lambda \sim I$$

$$\rightarrow \varepsilon \sim I$$

$$\Lambda \sim (I \cup N)$$

$$S \sim (N \cup U \cup T(s))$$

$$(N \cup U \cup T(s)) (I \cup N \Lambda)$$

$$R \rightarrow T(I \cup U \cup T(s))$$

$$U \cup U \cup U \rightarrow T(\Lambda(G))$$

$$R \rightarrow (U \cup U \cup U)$$

$$\forall \mathbf{x} \in R : \mathbf{x} \subset [\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)] \subset \lambda \sim f(x)$$

$$\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) \cdot G = \left[\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta} \right]$$

$$\mathbf{u}_1 \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) \cdot G = \left[\frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta}}{\Delta} \right]$$

$$\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) \cdot G = \left[\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{F} : V &\rightarrow U, \sum_{f \subset g} f(g) = \sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h, \\
x \in V * U &\leftrightarrow \exists y \in U : f(y) = x, x \in T(s) \leftrightarrow \exists s \in S : x = T(s), \\
x \in f \circ g &\leftrightarrow x \in T(s) \\
G \cup \mathbf{L}'(x_i) &\rightarrow \left[\frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta} \right] \\
\sum_{f \subset g} f(g) &= \sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h
\end{aligned}$$

As previously noted, we don't know the exact position of x until it appears in the integral expression of the partial derivative. Therefore, let $\mathbf{L}(x_i) \cdot G = [\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y), \exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x), \forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)]$. However, $\mathbf{L}(x_i) = x_i = T(s)$, where $T(s)$ is a Descartes domain-codomain pair in a set of possible function variable sets s_n , so we further know that $s_n \equiv s$. Note that we require a set T in our function space $T(s)$ so that, once the function $T(s)$ is designated, we may propose the existence of a unique element x (a cardinality of 1) that is guaranteed to occupy the domain of U and a unique element y that is guaranteed to occupy the codomain of U . However, one could say that this is not sufficiently general for all real numbers because position of the number y is not known. Therefore, let $U \equiv \{\alpha \cdot x^2 + \beta \cdot x + \gamma | \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in C\}$ so that no matter what the domain of a function is, it always return an element of U . However, we don't want to solve a system of linear equations because the implicit nonlinear property of U must be preserved. For any given input $y \in N$, we want to know the function f and the constant γ that returns the result $x \in N$. Solving: $f(y) = x$ by rewriting γ as a function of y and x renders $f(y) = x = \gamma(y, x)$. Therefore, let $\gamma(y, x) \equiv \forall \gamma \in C([y]_{\gamma} = x)$ and $f(y) = x = \gamma(y, x) \equiv \forall \gamma \in C(\forall \gamma \in C[y]_{\gamma} = x)$. However, this is a single-element cardinality on the RHS. Therefore, the solution must be $U \mapsto V \leftrightarrow \sum_{f \subset g} f(g) = \sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h$. In this case, $\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) = \left[\frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta} \right]$.

What then, therefore is the relationship between space-time and logic space? An application of affine geometry and tensor calculus may give us an idea.

In vector calculus, we learn that all vector spaces require a metric to define orthonormality and that the relationship between calculus and number theory turns on the action of a differentiation operator acting on a set of functions - in other words, the product rule is determined by a geometric operation that we may call an "addition" operator. This operator is, of course, the Lie bracket, which is defined as $\mathbf{x} \times \mathbf{y} = \Omega \cdot \mathbf{x} \times \mathbf{y}$, where it is the antisymmetric part of the tensor product $\mathbf{x} \otimes \mathbf{y}$ that gives rise to the affine space. This defines the Lie group, as well as the affine space as we understand it. What is the Lie matrix? It is the matrix that, by a coordinate transform operation, decomposes a tensor product into a symmetric and anti-symmetric part (a moment of inertia tensor and a tensor of gyroscopic motion). Nevertheless, put in more fundamental terms, the Lie matrix is just a tensor product.

Now, let's go away from number theory and go back to logic space. We know that functions, in their most general sense, can have space-time as their input and output, so we can say that space-time and logic space both have functions as their mathematical objects. However, since the number 0 is a

map of the space-time, they are also assigned a value. This means that we then must take maps from numbers to space-time to be the most basic values. However, we know that numbers can be described by, for instance, a ratio of 2 prime numbers, which means that we can say that these are the objects of logic. However, the relationship between logic and space-time is determined by a metric and a set of logical operations. This suggests that a logical operation yields a reconfiguration of space. More importantly, it behooves us to note that logic space and number theory are equivalent, in the sense that any function can be expressed as a number. This means that the relationship between logic and space-time is determined by a metric and a set of logical operations. This suggests that a logical operation yields a reconfiguration of space.

What we have just suggested is that the relationship between space and time acts as an equivalence between space and time and therefore a single logical operator. By using the structure of the equivalence, we may posit an equivalence between space and time by way of the simplest logical operator - that of an identity matrix. That is, there is an identity operation on a function space.

Let $I \mapsto [1\ 0\ 0\ 1]$. If a function F is isomorphic to I then we say $I = F = \frac{dF}{d\lambda} \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau}$, where $\lambda \equiv \frac{y}{x}$, with the understanding that if y and x are coordinates in space and time, then y describes the time coordinate and x describes the space coordinate. Given this understanding, we may then write the identity as $\mathbf{x} \equiv \mathbf{y} = [yx] = \frac{y}{x} = \tau = \lambda \mapsto I = [1\ 0\ 0\ 1] \equiv \frac{dF}{d\lambda} \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau}$. In this case, the metric is $g = \mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{y} = |\mathbf{x}|^2|\mathbf{y}|^2$, where $[yx] = \frac{y}{x} = \tau = \lambda \mapsto I = [1\ 0\ 0\ 1] \equiv \frac{dF}{d\lambda} \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau}$. In this case, the metric is $g = \mathbf{x} \cdot \mathbf{y} = |\mathbf{x}|^2|\mathbf{y}|^2$, where $|\mathbf{x}|^2 = x^2$ and $|\mathbf{y}|^2 = y^2$; furthermore, when x and y are specified in space and time, the statement $\mathbf{x} \equiv \mathbf{y} = \tau = \lambda$ is equivalent to the statement $\mathbf{x} \equiv \mathbf{y} = \tau = [1\ 0\ 0\ 1] \equiv \frac{dF}{d\lambda} \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau}$, which is a metric for the identity operator $\tau \equiv \mathbf{x} \equiv \mathbf{y} = [1\ 0\ 0\ 1]$.

Now we take to describe a relation between functions, with the understanding that $\frac{dF}{d\lambda} \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau}$ defines a functional value in itself and on a manifold. Note that $\mathbf{x} = \tau = \mathbf{y} = \lambda = \frac{dF}{d\lambda} \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau} \equiv [\tau\ 0]$ is a vector with a single element and has a tensor product form of $[\tau\ 0\ 0\ \tau]$. This means that the relationship between $\mathbf{x} \equiv \mathbf{y} = \tau = \lambda = \frac{dF}{d\lambda} \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau}$ and $\mathbf{x} = |\mathbf{x}|^2|\mathbf{y}|^2$ is a tensor product that is therefore a linear transformation. The transformation $F(\mathbf{x}) \equiv \frac{dF}{d\lambda}$ is a natural transformation over the identity operator, which is also a functional. This then implies that $\mathbf{x} = |\mathbf{x}|^2|\mathbf{y}|^2 \equiv F(X) + F(Y)$. Therefore, $\mathbf{x} \equiv \mathbf{y} = \tau = \lambda = \frac{dF}{d\lambda} \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau} = [1\ 0\ 0\ 1]$ defines a vector with a single element and has a tensor product form of $[\tau\ 0\ 0\ \tau]$. This means that the relationship between $\mathbf{x} \equiv \mathbf{y} = \tau = \lambda = \frac{dF}{d\lambda} \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau}$ and $\mathbf{x} = |\mathbf{x}|^2|\mathbf{y}|^2$ is a tensor product that is therefore a linear transformation. The transformation $F(\mathbf{x}) \equiv \frac{dF}{d\lambda}$ is a natural transformation over the identity operator, which is also a functional. This then implies that $\mathbf{x} = |\mathbf{x}|^2|\mathbf{y}|^2 \equiv F(X) + F(Y)$. Therefore, we can say that there is a relationship between x and y , understood in terms of a spatial metric, that is equivalent to the relationship between tensor products and Euclidean space understood in terms of a Euclidean metric. Consequently, the relationship between τ and N understood in terms of a logic operator is equivalent to the relationship between tensor products and Euclidean space understood in terms

of a Euclidean metric. Therefore, there is a relationship between x and y , understood in terms of a spatial metric, that is equivalent to the relationship between tensor products and Euclidean space understood in terms of a Euclidean metric. Consequently, the relationship between τ and N understood in terms of a logic operator is equivalent to the relationship between tensor products and Euclidean space understood in terms of a Euclidean metric.

Therefore, there is a relationship between x and y , understood in terms of a spatial metric, that is equivalent to the relationship between tensor products and Euclidean space understood in terms of a Euclidean metric. Consequently, the relationship between τ and N understood in terms of a logic operator is equivalent to the relationship between tensor products and Euclidean space understood in terms of a Euclidean metric.

Now that we have established this fundamental relationship between space-time and logic space, we may describe an equivalence between space-time and a set of axioms. Consider the logic operator $\exists$. This operator states that there is an existence statement of the form $x \equiv \exists y \in N | F(y) = x$. This then implies that there is an equivalence between space and time because a spatial comparison implies an action on a function.

Consider the following: $N \subset Z$ and $Z \subset R$. If $\exists x \in N : F(x) = y$, then x maps to y . In this case, $N \subset Z \subset R \subset R' \equiv R^\times$, where $x \in R' \subset R$. Now, we may state that a vector space is described by its scalars and vectors. We may therefore say $\mathcal{F} \cdot \mathbf{x} = 3 \cdot \mathbf{x}$. This implies that x , described as a function, is also a vector. Now, let x be a function of y , so that $\exists x \in R | \exists y \in R : x(y) = \tau \equiv \lambda$. Given that $\exists x : F(x) = \tau \equiv \lambda$ and $\mathcal{F} : R \rightarrow R$, then $\mathcal{F} = 3$. We can therefore say that there is a direct relationship between logic and the dimension of space, as defined by the number of points per unit area of some geometric shape in a given space. This relationship also describes a direct relationship between the dimensionality of space and function theory via the equivalence $\exists x : F(x) = \tau \equiv \lambda \equiv R \rightarrow R \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau}$. In this case, we may define $R \mapsto R \equiv R \mapsto R$, which is equivalent to $\frac{d}{dR}[\mathbf{x}^k \mapsto \mathbf{x}^j] \equiv \frac{d}{dR}[k \mapsto j]$. Consequently, the logic $\forall x \in R, \exists y \rightarrow \infty, \pi \cdot x \equiv \pi \cdot y \equiv R \mapsto R \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau} \equiv \frac{dF}{d\lambda} \equiv [x^k \mapsto x^j, y^k \mapsto y^j, j \mapsto k, k \mapsto j]$ is equivalent to the statement that the equivalence class $\pi \cdot R$ serves to map a real number to a real number, with the understanding that π is the number which is the ratio of the circumference of the circle to its diameter.

Now that we've developed a fundamental relationship between space-time and logic, we may restate the relationship between tensor products and Euclidean space in terms of a Euclidean coordinate system under a metric. Consider the relationship $\mathbf{F}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{dF}{d\lambda} \equiv \frac{dF}{d\tau} \equiv [x^k \mapsto x^j, y^k \mapsto y^j, j \mapsto k, k \mapsto j]$

What then, therefore is the relationship between space-time and logic space? Is actual space a subset of logic space or are they entwined somehow? What remains for us to consider are the following possibilities:

1. The logic partition is appropriated from a redefinition of space-time, hence yielding the equation $G' \equiv M \cap X'$.
2. The logic partition is a subset of the space-time transformation, hence

yielding the equation $X' \equiv M' \cap G'$.

3. The logic partition is a bijection of the space-time transformation, hence yielding the equation $M \equiv M' \cap G'$
4. The logic partition is a logical set constructed from the space-time transformation, hence yielding the equation $X' \equiv G \cap M'$
5. The logic partition is a discrete, nonholonomic representation of the space-time transformation, hence yielding the equation $G' \equiv M' \cap G$
6. The logic partition is another dimension of space-time, yielding the equation $X \equiv M \cap G'$

Clearly, each of these definitions is a Cartesian product subject to the following assumption: $X' \times M' = Z$ where $Z \equiv (G' \cap G) \cup (M' \cap M) \cup (X' \cap X)$ or, is an unordered set of elements from each of the combination functions.

And, in this case, we have the following mappings:

$$\begin{aligned}
I &= \left\{ \prod_N \cup \cup_N \circ S_N^T \right\} \times \left\{ \prod_{N+1} \cup \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right\} \\
\rightarrow I &= \left\{ \left(\prod_N \cup \cup_N \circ S_N^T \right) \mid \forall N \in N \right\} \times \left\{ \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right) \mid \forall N+1 \in N \right\} \\
&\rightarrow I = P \times Q \\
P &= \left\{ \left(\prod_N \cup \cup_N \circ S_N^T \right) \mid \forall N \in N \right\} \\
Q &= \left\{ \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right) \mid \forall N+1 \in N \right\} \\
\rightarrow I &= \forall N \in N, \cdot \left(\prod_N \cup \cup_N \circ S_N^T \right) \times \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right) \\
I &= \forall N \in N, \left(\prod_M^N \cup_M^N \circ S_M^T \right)^T \times \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right) \\
I &= \forall N \in N, \left(\prod_M \cup_M \right)^T = \left(\prod_M \cup_M \right)^\dagger \\
\rightarrow I &= \forall N \in I, \left(\prod_M \cup_M \right)^T \times \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right) \\
I &= \forall N \in N, \circ \left(\prod_M \cup_M \right)^T \times \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I &= \forall N \in N, \circ \left(\prod_M \cup_M \right)^T \times \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right) \\
&\quad X \cup M = Z \\
&\Rightarrow Z = \left(\prod_{x \in X} \cup_{x \in M} \right) \cup \left(\prod_{x \in M} \cup_{x \in X} \right) \\
&\Rightarrow \mathbf{z} = \left(\prod_{x \in X} \cup_{x \in M} \right) \times \left(\prod_{x \in M} \cup_{x \in X} \right) \\
&\Rightarrow \mathbf{z} = \left(\left(\prod_{x \in X} \cup_{x \in M} \right) \times \left(\prod_{x \in M} \cup_{x \in X} \right) \right)^T \\
&\Rightarrow \mathbf{z} = \left(\left(\prod_{x \in X} \cup_{x \in M} \right) \times \left(\prod_{y \in M} \cup_{y \in X} \right) \right)^T \\
&\Rightarrow \mathbf{z} = \left(\left(\prod_{x \in X} \cup_{x \in M} \right) \widetilde{\times} \left(\prod_{x \in M} \cup_{x \in X} \right) \right)^T \\
&\Rightarrow \mathbf{z} = \forall N \in N, \left(\prod_M \cup_M \right)^T \times \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right) \\
&\mathbf{z} = \forall N \in N, \left(\prod_M \cup_M \right)^T \times \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right) \\
&\mathbf{z} = \forall N \in N, \circ \left(\prod_M \cup_M \right)^T \times \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right) \\
&\mathbf{z} = \circ \left(\forall N \in N, \left(\prod_M \cup_M \right)^T \times \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right) \right)^T \\
&\mathbf{z} = \circ \left(\forall N \in N, \left(\prod_M \cup_M \right)^T \times \left(\prod_{N+1} \cup_{N+1} \circ S_{N+1}^T \right) \right)^T \\
&\mathbf{z} = \circ \left(\prod_{x \in X} \cup_{x \in M}, \prod_{y \in M} \cup_{y \in X} \right)^T \\
&\mathbf{z} = \circ \left(\prod_{x \in X} \cup_{x \in M}, \prod_{y \in M} \cup_{y \in X} \right)^T
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\left(\prod_{x \in X} \cup_{x \in M} \right)^T &= \left(\prod_{y \in M} \cup_{y \in X} \right)^T \\
\rightarrow \mathbf{z} &= \left(\prod_{x \in X} \cup_{x \in M}, \prod_{y \in M} \cup_{y \in X} \right)^T \\
\mathbf{z} &= \left(\prod_{x \in X}^{N+1} \cup_{x \in M}^{N+1} \right)^T = \left(\prod_{y \in M}^{N+1} \cup_{y \in X}^{N+1} \right)^T
\end{aligned}$$

Let $F_N \equiv \prod_{x \in X}^{N+1} \cup_{x \in M}^{N+1}$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{z} &= F_N^\dagger = G_N^\dagger \\
F_N^\dagger &= G_N^\dagger \\
\rightarrow \mathbf{z} &= F_1
\end{aligned}$$

Thus the dimension of our space-time manifold is preserved with a dimension $N + 1$. **1.1 Step 2**

In the following, we will arrive at the point of an interesting result, namely, the derivation of another condition as follows: $\mathcal{P} = \mathcal{N} \cup \mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{O}$. The proof for which is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{P} &= \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{S} \times \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{O} \\
\mathcal{P} &= \mathcal{N} \times \mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{O} \\
\mathcal{P} &= \mathcal{N} \cup \mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{A} \times \mathcal{O} \\
\mathcal{P} &= \mathcal{N} \cup \mathcal{S} \cup \mathcal{A} \cup \mathcal{O}
\end{aligned}$$

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} f_x$$

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} \cup_{y \in G} g_y \circ f_x$$

There is an invariant in this system, namely, that

$$\prod_N^{N+1} \cup_N^{N+1} \circ S_N^T = \prod_N^{N+1} \cup_N^{N+1} \circ S_N^T$$

Thus, we have an interesting result, namely that the space-time manifold and the logic manifold are one and the same,

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} \cup_{y \in F} g_y \circ f_x$$

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} F$$

We have just derived a new set F which is a subset of the logic set defined by G . Thus we know that the space-time manifold is a subset of the logic manifold, implying that

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} \cup_{y \in G} g_y \circ f_x$$

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} \cup_{y \in G} \cup_{x \in F} g_y \circ f_x$$

$$\cup_{x \in F} g_y \circ f_x = \cup_{y \in G} \cup_{x \in F} g_y \circ f_x$$

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} \cup_{x \in F} g_y \circ f_x$$

$$g_y \circ f_x = g_y \circ f_x$$

$$\cup_{x \in S} g_y \circ f_x = \cup_{x \in S} g_y \circ f_x$$

$$\cup_{x \in S} g_y \circ f_x = g_y$$

$$\cup_{x \in S} g_y \circ f_x = \cup_{z \in F} f_z$$

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} \cup_{z \in F} f_z$$

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} \cup_{z \in G} g_y \circ f_z$$

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} \cup_{y \in G} g_y \circ (\cup_{z \in G} g_y \circ f_z)$$

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} \cup_{y \in G} g_y \circ z$$

$$z = \cup_{x \in S} \cup_{y \in G} z$$

$$z = z$$

$$(\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)) \cup \left[\frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta} \right] = G$$

$$G \cap \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{g}) = \mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i)$$

Consider the following definition: if $\mathbf{u} \cdot \mathbf{L}'(x_i) \subset G$

1.1.1 Step 2.1

Furthermore, we will also construct a new set K as follows:

$$K = S \circ F \circ G$$

$$K = \{\circ_{x \in S} \circ_{y \in G} g_y \circ z \mid z \subset F\}$$

$$K = \{g_y \circ (\circ_{x \in S} z) \mid z \subset F\}$$

We see that $K = G$

$$K \subset G$$

$$K = G$$

$$\prod_M^N \cup_M^N = \sum_M^N \circ_M^N$$

1.1.2 Step 2.2

However, consider what happens when we transform the algebra using the definition of a generalized inverse:

$$K = \{\circ_{x \in S} \circ_{y \in G} g_y \circ z \mid z \subset F\}$$

$$K^\dagger = \{\circ_{x \in S^\dagger} \circ_{y \in G^\dagger} g_y^\dagger \circ z^\dagger \mid z^\dagger \subset F^\dagger\}$$

$$K^\dagger = \{\circ_{x \in S^\dagger} \circ_{y \in G^\dagger} g_y^\dagger \circ z^\dagger \mid z^\dagger \subset F\}$$

$$K^\dagger = \{\circ_{x \in S^\dagger} \circ_{y \in G^\dagger} g_y^\dagger \circ z \mid z \subset F\}$$

$$K^\dagger = \{\circ_{x \in S^\dagger} \circ_{y \in G^\dagger} g_y^\dagger \circ z \mid z \subset F\}$$

$$K^\dagger = \{\circ_{x \in S^\dagger} \circ_{y \in G^\dagger} g_y^\dagger \mid z \subset F\}$$

$$K^\dagger = \{\circ_{x \in S^\dagger} z \mid z \subset F\}$$

$$K^\dagger = \{\circ_{x \in S^\dagger} \circ_{y \in F} g_y^\dagger | z \subset F\}$$

$$K^\dagger = \{\circ_{x \in S^\dagger} \circ_{y \in G} g_y^\dagger | z \subset F\}$$

$$\rightarrow K^\dagger = \{\circ_{x \in S^\dagger} \circ_{y \in G} g_y^\dagger | z \subset F\}$$

$$K^\dagger = \{z \circ_{x \in S^\dagger} \circ_{y \in G} g_y^\dagger | z \subset F\}$$

The fractal morphism would build upon the basic equations of the submanifold and iteratively build on them to form the space-time supermanifold. This is done by using two basic elements:

1. A logic vector space V which is a set of vectors that represent the logical relationships of the components of the submanifold.
2. An operator $\mathcal{P}$ which is a function that transforms the vectors in V into elements that are part of the space-time supermanifold.

The fractal morphism can then be expressed as:

$$F : (V, \mathcal{P}) \rightarrow (\Omega_\Lambda, C') \quad \text{such that} \quad \Omega_{\Lambda'} \leftrightarrow \mathcal{P}(V)$$

This is the basic equation of the fractal morphism. The fractal morphism can then be further iterated upon to create more complex structures. This will be discussed in detail in the following section.

Let $\mathcal{A}$ be a logic vector space, the the submanifold of $\mathcal{A}$, namely $\mathcal{B}$ is defined by:

$$\mathcal{B} = \left\{ \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A} : \mathbf{b} = \sum_{i=1}^n f_i \circ \psi_i(\mathbf{x}) \right\}$$

where $\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{A}$ and $f_i(\mathbf{x})$ is a mapping to the logic vector space and ψ_i is the mapping to the space-time supermanifold.

To extend $\mathcal{B}$ to the space-time supermanifold, we use the transformation

$$\mathbf{y} = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{f}_i \circ \psi_i(\mathbf{x})$$

where $\mathbf{f}_i(\mathbf{x})$ is now a mapping to the space-time supermanifold and ψ_i is the mapping to the logic vector space.

By substituting this transformation in the original set equation, we get:

$$\mathcal{B} = \left\{ \mathbf{b} \in \mathcal{A} : \mathbf{b} = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{f}_i \circ \psi_i(\mathbf{x}) \right\}$$

Hence, we see that $\mathcal{B}$ is extended from a logic vector space submanifold to a space-time supermanifold, by using the transformation $\mathbf{y} = \sum_{i=1}^n \mathbf{f}_i \circ \psi_i(\mathbf{x})$.

$$K^\dagger = \{z \circ_{x \in S^\dagger} \circ_{y \in G} g_y^\dagger | z \subset F\}$$

$$K^\dagger = \{\circ(\cup_{x \in S} \cup_{y \in G} g_y^\dagger) | z \subset F\}$$

Let

$$F_x = \{F_1, F_2, \dots, F_n\}$$

Then

$$K^\dagger = \circ(\cup_{x \in S} \cup_{y \in F_x} g_y^\dagger)$$

$$K^\dagger = \circ\left(\prod_{z \in F} g_y^\dagger\right)$$

$$K^\dagger = \circ\left(\prod_{z \in F} g_y^\dagger\right)$$

$$K^\dagger = \{z \cdot \prod_{z \in F} g_y^\dagger | z \subset F\}$$

Hence, the primal energy number expression for the fractal morphism is

$$E = \Omega_\Lambda \left(z \cdot \prod_{z \in F} g_y^\dagger \right)$$